

Two Nothotaxa at New Rank in *Hylotelephium* (Crassulaceae)

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Abstract—The nothospecies *Hylotelephium* ×*bergeri* and *Hylotelephium* ×*zhiguliense* are demoted to subspecific rank as *Hylotelephium telephium* nothosubsp. ×*bergeri* and *Hylotelephium telephium* nothosubsp. ×*zhiguliense*.

The nothospecific combinations *Hylotelephium* ×*bergeri* and *Hylotelephium* ×*zhiguliense* refer to the respective hybrids *Hylotelephium maximum* (L.) Holub × *Hylotelephium telephium* (L.) H.Ohba and *Hylotelephium telephium* × *Hylotelephium ruprechtii* (Jalas) Tzvelev. However, these combinations are only correct when the parent taxa are treated at the generic level. Since *H. maximum* and *H. ruprechtii* are now usually considered subspecies of *H. telephium*, the following names at new rank are needed:

Hylotelephium telephium* nothosubsp. ×*bergeri (Raym.-Hamet) M.van der Meer
stat. nov.

≡ *Sedum bergeri* Raym.-Hamet (pro sp.)

—Bull. Mus. Natl. Hist. Nat. xv. 488 (1909)

≡ *Hylotelephium* ×*bergeri* (Raym.-Hamet) B.Bock

—Bull. Soc. Bot. Centre-Ouest 42: 264 (2012)

Hylotelephium telephium subsp. *maximum* (L.) H.Ohba ×

Hylotelephium telephium (L.) H.Ohba subsp. *telephium*

Etymology: ‘Cette espèce est dédiée à M. le Professeur D^r Alwin Berger, Directeur du Jardin Hambury à la Mortola, qui a bien voulu mettre à ma

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disposition un nombre considérable de Crassulacées vivantes. Je le prie ici d'agréer mes meilleurs remerciements.' (Hamet 1909)

Hylotelephium telephium* nothosubsp. ×*zhiguliense (Tzvelev) M.van der Meer
stat. nov.

≡ *Hylotelephium zhiguliense* Tzvelev

—Novosti Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 29: 135 (1993)

Hylotelephium telephium subsp. *ruprechtii* (Jalas) H.Ohba ×

Hylotelephium telephium (L.) H.Ohba subsp. *telephium*

Etymology: Presumably named for the occurrence in the Zhiguli Mountains, Samara Oblast, Russia.

Literature

Hamet, R. (1909). Sedum nouveaux de l'Herbier du Muséum. *Bull. Mus. Natl. Hist. Nat.*, xv, 488–490.